

Insights on the Lunar Mg-Suite formation looking at Flakstadøya anorthositic complex (Lofoten, Norway)

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Introduction: The origin of lunar highlands and the genetic relationship between ferroan anorthosites (FANs) and the Mg-suite remain debated. Recent studies on lunar meteorites suggest a common origin among these rock types through serial magmatism [1], challenging the classic Lunar Magma Ocean model [2] [4]. Terrestrial massif-type anorthosites [a] valuable analogues to test the lunar primordial crust formation hypotheses. We investigated the Nesland area (Flakstadøya Island, Lofoten, Norway), where dunitic masses occur within a Proterozoic anorthosite complex [4] [5] to shed light on how Mg suite rocks can form.

Methods: Our approach integrates multi-scale SWIR hyperspectral remote sensing with field mapping, optical microscopy, and SEM-EDS microanalysis.

Fig.1 a) Dunite masses spreading olivines within the anorthosite host rocks in Nesland (Flakstadøya complex, Lofoten Norway); b) Troctolite-dunite transition as seen through optical microscope (Cross Polarized)

Remote sensing successfully discriminated the main lithological units at both regional and outcrop scales, revealing distinctive spectral patterns around dunite-anorthosite contacts. Petrographic and microchemical data documented the textural and compositional relationships between olivine-rich and plagioclase-rich domains, providing constraints on the interaction processes between ultramafic and anorthositic materials.

Results: Field evidences supported by spectral surveys and petrographic observations show how troctolites in Flakstadøya complex were likely formed through erosion of ultramafic layers and subsequent dispersion of mafic minerals into the anorthositic host. This finding suggests a process of Mg suite formation which is well conceivable within a serial magmatism framework during lunar primordial crust formation. Overall our results demonstrate the potential of multi-scale hyperspectral mapping integrated with a multi-analytical laboratory approach for investigating anorthositic terrains on Earth as analog of lunar highlands.

References: [1] Gross et al. (2014). *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 388, 318-328. [2] Warren (1985) *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 13(1), 201-240. [3] Elkins-Tanton et al. (2020), *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 304(3-4), 326-336. [4] Markl, (1998) *Journal of Petrology*, 39(8), 1425-1452. [5] Corfu (2004) *Journal of Petrology*, 45(9), 1799-1819.

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